

EVALUATION OF THE ORAL PRESENTATION OF STUDENTS IN THEIR ENGLISH FOR ACADEMIC PURPOSES AND STUDY SKILLS (EAPSS) MODULE

Leovigildo Lito D. Mallillin¹ⁱ,
Deny Daniel²

¹Lecturer Dr.,

Faculty of Business and Management Studies,
Gulf College, Sultanate of Oman

²Lecturer Ms.,

Faculty of Business and Management Studies,
Gulf College, Sultanate of Oman

Abstract:

One of the skills a student develops in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) is their oral presentation. It is a skill wherein students do a presentation in front of the audience inside the classroom. The study aims to determine the performance level of students in their oral presentation in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) module along the area of content of the oral presentation in terms of introduction and structure, key points and body, conclusion and references and along the area of execution of the oral presentation in terms of speech, personal energy, audience impact and time management. The study used the descriptive research design because it describes the performance level of the students in their oral presentation of the English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) particularly the content and execution which is appropriate in the current investigation. The subjects of the study are the students of Higher Education Institution (HEI) registered in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) module. The study comprised of thirty (30) respondents only. Random sampling is employed in the study as this method investigates the oral presentation of the respondents in their oral presentation on content and execution of the presentation of the study. Results show that the performance level of the students in terms of the content of the presentation needs improvement in the introductory part, good in presenting the key points and ideas and moderate regarding conclusion and reference. Furthermore, in terms of execution, their speech also needs improvement, time management and impact on the audience is moderate and their personal energy level is good.

ⁱ Correspondence: email loviedsunbright_0722@yahoo.com.ph

Keywords: English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS), evaluation of the oral presentation, oral presentation, content of oral presentation, execution of oral presentation

1. Introduction

One of the skills a student develops in English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) is their oral presentation. It is a skill wherein students make a presentation, in front of the audience inside the classroom on a particular topic using audio-visual aids like projector, IPTV, power point slides and videos. It can be done in group or individual. It is a part of the assessment of the students. They are being evaluated on their oral presentation inside the classroom on the basis of the learning outcomes they have achieved. However, prior to their oral presentation, students are given the necessary techniques and tools for proper oral presentation. Students are required to practice prior to their final presentation. They are provided the necessary tips and techniques in oral presentation for improving and enhancing their performance (Lin, and Hwang, 2018).

Hence, motivation is needed for the students to focus since English is a foreign language for them. This has an effect on their oral presentation especially when they encounter unfamiliar words, they do not have much exposure to speaking in front of an audience and have no adequate opportunity to converse in English. They have difficulties in the communication process because they are not exposed to it, so proper motivation will help the students to improve their presentation in all aspects. They learn English as a foreign language and they are native in terms of Arabic language. Their pronunciation is being affected. Motivation is the key for their learning and exposure to oral presentation. This can influence students to learn and to improve their skills in the English language. Therefore, English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills will help them improve their skills in their oral presentation as part of their assessment (Liang, and Kelsen, 2018).

Nevertheless, there are two areas in the assessment of their oral presentation, they are assessed on the content of the oral presentation and are assessed on the execution of the oral presentation. Before the students are given the task of doing a presentation skills on the oral presentation are taught step by step, especially on the procedure and techniques for better oral presentation output. Hence, content of the oral presentation is based on the sequence of the content as to introduction which is the eye opener of the topic for oral presentation. Providing an interesting introduction will get the attention of the audience. The introduction is followed by the key points and body; it is important because it explains the details of the presentation. Furthermore, the conclusion explains the summary and synopsis of the topic of the presentation. Apart from the content, they are also taught on the referencing aspect as part of the institutional requirements like text citation and Harvard referencing style. The practice of various techniques in the oral presentation encourages students to excel in presenting

their topic. It explains the process of their presentation and helps them develop their speaking in front of the audience. It demonstrates and corresponds to provide quality output in their assessment in the oral presentation. It incorporates strategies and techniques in the oral presentation effectively. It increases to boost their confidence in speaking (van Ginkel, Gulikers, Biemans, and Mulder, 2017).

In addition, assessment of the oral presentation among the students is also based on the execution in terms of speech- whether the pronunciation is accurate, with conviction and with clarity on the word usages, tone of voice, audibility and control of nervousness. The sound quality of speech based on the clarity of the word that influences the oral presentation like context support, and sentences to enhance coherence, semantics, and predictability of the word during the oral presentation. Mechanics of speech is a requirement that underlies the proper matching of words based on the topic to be presented. Clear speech during the presentation will give a better performance on the oral presentation. This is to test the knowledge of the students whether the principles and theories are followed during their training and enhancement of their assessment (Signoret, Johnsrude, Classon, and Rudner, 2018). Similarly, their confidence and their personal energy add to their performance level.

How the presentation is done reveals the personality of the person. Personal energy requires confidence and readiness on the task in the oral presentation and to establish competency in the assessment in moderate presentation skills (Ringeisen, Rohrman, Bürgermeister, and Tibubos, 2017). They need to avoid reading during the presentation. Mastery is a must where they can develop confidence and boost their morale in the presentation. They need to address the audience with confident personality as a whole showing their expertise in speaking in front of the audience. Having a great deal of personal energy enhances student ability towards oral presentation since they recognize the trending of the motivation of the students in terms of belief, goals, behavior and emotion during the oral presentation (Wlodkowski, and Ginsberg, 2017). This is supported by the study of (van Ginkel, Gulikers, Biemans, and Mulder, 2017) on oral presentation competency that enhances student knowledge in the oral presentation in improving their skills in the module for the assessment which increases their morale and personal energy during the presentation.

On the other hand, audience impact is one of the criteria in the assessment of the oral presentation. Audiences are the observers inside the classroom for the oral presentation. They are observing the presenter/s to adapt ideas for the improvement of the skills in the presentation. Impressing the audience on the presentation will motivate them to improve also their skills in the oral presentation. It explores the role of the presenter/s to the mechanics of observation comes from the audience which is very timely and important in their presentation also which is expected from the presenters. Audience impact adds confidence to the presenters to show support during the oral presentation (Hanusch, and Tandoc, 2019).

Nevertheless, students or presenters are given a time frame for their oral presentation. This is to measure on how they manage their time properly. They are

required to finish their presentation based on the allocated time frame they have. Timeframe determines the presentation managed by the students to include the number of slides needed in the presentation (Stuart, and Grove, 2017).

Therefore, execution in the oral presentation will validate the performance of the students in the assessment of the module in English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS).

2. Statement of the Problem

1. What is the performance level of students on their oral presentation in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) module along the area of

A. Content of the Oral Presentation

- a) Introduction and Structure;
- b) Key points and Body;
- c) Conclusion;
- d) References.

B. Execution of the Oral Presentation

- a) Speech;
- b) Personal Energy;
- c) Audience Impact;
- d) Time Management.

2. Is there a significant relationship between the content of the oral presentation and the execution of the oral presentation among the respondents?

2.1 Hypothesis

There is no significant relationship between the content of the oral presentation and the execution of the oral presentation among the respondents.

3. Research Design

The study used the descriptive research design because it describes the performance level of the students in their oral presentation of the English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills particularly in their oral presentation on content and execution which is appropriate in the current investigation (Omair, 2015).

3.1 Respondents of the Study

The subjects of the study are the students of a Higher Education Institution (HEI) registered in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS) module. The study comprised of thirty (30) respondents only.

3.2 Sampling Techniques

Random sampling is employed in the study as this method investigates the oral presentation of the respondents in their oral presentation on content and execution of the presentation and a technique to identify the standard deviation of the study (Endo, Watanabe, and Yamamoto, 2015).

4. Results

Table 1: Content of the oral presentation

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
1. Introduction and structure			
Very Poor	0	0	4.5
Poor	18	60	1
Moderate	10	33	2
Good	2	7	3
Very Good	0	0	4.5
2. Key points and body			
Very Poor	0	0	4.5
Poor	0	0	4.5
Moderate	16	53	1
Good	3	10	3
Very Good	11	37	2
3. Conclusion			
Very Poor	0	0	5
Poor	2	7	3
Moderate	24	80	1
Good	2	7	3
Very Good	2	7	3
4. References			
Very Poor	0	0	4.5
Poor	0	0	4.5
Moderate	26	87	1
Good	2	7	2.5
Very Good	2	7	2.5

Table 1 shows the results of the content of the oral presentation of the respondents. Introduction and structure shows poor with a frequency of 18 or 60% among the respondents, key points and body shows moderate with a frequency of 16 or 53% among the respondents, conclusion shows moderate with a frequency of 24 or 80% among the respondents, and references shows moderate with a frequency of 26 or 87% among the respondents.

Table 2: Execution of the Oral Presentation

Indicators	Frequency	Percentage	Ranking
1. Speech			
Very Poor	0	0	4.5
Poor	17	57	1
Moderate	12	40	2
Good	1	3	3
Very Good	0	0	4.5
2. Personal energy			
Very Poor	0	0	4.5
Poor	0	0	4.5
Moderate	19	63	1
Good	6	20	2
Very Good	5	17	3
3. Audience impact			
Very Poor	0	0	4
Poor	0	0	4
Moderate	28	93	1
Good	2	7	2
Very Good	0	0	4
4. Time Management			
Very Poor	0	0	4.5
Poor	5	17	2
Moderate	24	80	1
Good	1	3	3
Very Good	0	0	4.5

Table 2 shows the results of the execution of the oral presentation of the respondents. Speech is poor with a frequency of 17 or 57% among the respondents, personal energy is moderate with a frequency of 19 or 63% among the respondents, audience impact is moderate with a frequency of 28 or 93% among the respondents, and time management is moderate with a frequency of 24 or 80% among the respondents.

Table 3: Results of the weighted mean and corresponding interpretation of the content of oral presentation of the respondents

Indicators	VP	P	M	G	VG	WM	SD	Interpretation
1. Introduction and structure	0	18	10	2	0	2.47	0.404	Poor
2. Key points and body	0	0	16	3	11	3.83	0.497	Good
3. Conclusion	0	2	24	2	2	3.13	0.452	Moderate
4. References	0	0	26	2	2	3.20	0.457	Moderate
Average Weighted Mean						3.16		Moderate

Table 3 shows the results of the weighted and the corresponding interpretation of the content of the oral presentation of the respondents. Introduction and structure is poor (WM=2.47), key points and body is good (WM=3.83), conclusion is moderate (WM=3.13), references is moderate (WM=3.20) and the overall (AWM=3.16) is moderate.

Table 4: Results of the weighted mean and corresponding interpretation of the execution of oral presentation of the respondents

Indicators	VP	P	M	G	VG	WM	SD	Interpretation
1. Speech	0	17	12	1	0	2.47	0.404	Poor
2. Personal energy	0	0	19	6	5	3.53	0.478	Good
3. Audience impact	0	0	28	2	0	3.07	0.448	Moderate
4. Time Management	0	5	24	1	0	2.87	0.434	Moderate
Average Weighted Mean						3.07		Moderate

Table 4 shows the results of the weighted mean and the corresponding interpretation of the execution of oral presentation of the respondents. Speech is poor (WM=2.47), personal energy is good (WM=3.53), audience impact is moderate (WM=3.07), time management is moderate (WM=2.87) and the overall (AWM=3.07) is moderate.

Table 5: Results of the significant relationship between the content of the oral presentation and execution of the oral presentation among the respondents

Variable	Computed r-value	Relationships *significant * not significant	Hypotheses *accepted *rejected
Introduction and Structure			
1. speech	0.074	not significant	accepted
2. personal energy	0.062	not significant	accepted
3. audience impact	0.066	not significant	accepted
4. time management	0.069	not significant	accepted
Key points and body			
1. speech	0.059	not significant	accepted
2. personal energy	0.049	not significant	accepted
3. audience impact	0.053	not significant	accepted
4. time management	0.055	not significant	accepted
Conclusion			
1. speech	0.066	not significant	accepted
2. personal energy	0.055	not significant	accepted
3. audience impact	0.059	not significant	accepted
4. time management	0.061	not significant	accepted
References			
1. speech	0.065	not significant	accepted
2. personal energy	0.054	not significant	accepted
3. audience impact	0.058	not significant	accepted
4. time management	0.060	not significant	accepted

Significant at 0.05 level, one-tailed test, df at 28 with critical r-value of 0.361

Table 5 shows the results of the significant relationship between the content of the oral presentation and the execution of the oral presentation among the respondents. When all variables are tested against each other it reveals that all computed r-value is lower than the critical r-value of 0.361. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the content of the oral presentation and the execution of the oral presentation among the respondents, the hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

5. Discussion

Oral presentation plays an important role in the skills needed by the students in their English for Academic Purposes and Study Skills (EAPSS). This is to enhance their ability to speak in front of the audience with confidence. It provides an individual to present worth with conviction to be trained confidently on oral presentation (Drew, 2018). It demonstrates a better knowledge on the content and understanding of the presentation task assigned, developing their skills on the implication pedagogy of the oral presentation (Poonpon, 2017).

Consequently, on the content of the oral presentation in the area of introduction, results show poor in which students do not have clear idea to provide an appealing introduction of their oral presentation in terms of introducing their topic, its objectives and what is expected from the presentation. Introduction must be clear since it is an eye opener of the topic presented in front of the audience. Structure and introduction of the oral presentation provides important techniques because the phenomena of the topic is delivered through text in the communication process which gives meaning, interpretation and context analysis of the topic to be presented (Krippendorff, 2018). It displays comprehensive clear and logical attention to the audience.

Moreover, on the content of the oral presentation in terms of body and key points explore the details to be presented. It addresses the issues to be discussed during the presentation. It must be appropriate to the audience for dissemination formation purposes. Through the presentation the audience learns, therefore the topic or subject must be accurate that can give information to the audience. To make the audience understand the topic better, the students should internalize the topic and content with proper justification. Developing an organized oral presentation can produce better output. Synthesising and analysing the presentation justifies the body and content of the oral presentation. It guides students effectively in their task of presenting the selected topic. Improvement on the oral presentation must be obtained by the students (Çetin, and Eymur, 2017).

In contrast, content in the oral presentation in the area of conclusion is moderate in which students know how to make summary of conclusion in their oral presentation. However; conclusion provides an integral lesson on the topic presented and gives emphasis on the details of the topic. Students need to know-how to give a better conclusion of the topic. The impact of conclusions and competency in the oral presentation strongly provides content of the topic on the part of the students (Murillo-Zamorano & Montanero, 2018). Conclusion is based on the topic presented by the students to give possible solution on the issue. It is a text that indicates the competitive conclusion as a synopsis of the topic presented. It must be authentic and interesting for the audience. It develops a better idea of information to the audience (Li, Li, Chi, & Ouyang, 2018).

In addition, content of the oral presentation in the area of references shows moderate in which students have a background on writing references required by them.

But they need to focus more in writing the text citation as appeared in their report submission together with the writing of their Harvard referencing. The institutional requirement for referencing is Harvard as the standard format for referencing in their project, assignment and in all their report tasks. Academic integrity is one of the problems in writing where students copy paste their assignment. This is sometimes neglected which is associated with plagiarism. Citation and referencing is a good practice among the students as they acknowledge the author of their references to their project or assignment. The main purpose is to identify the sources of their writing for proper analysis and review (Yap, Groen, Kamilova, Terzi, & Zvonareva, 2018).

Furthermore, on the execution of the oral presentation in the area of speech shows poor outcome which means many students have difficulties in their oral presentation since most words they encounter are unfamiliar and very difficult to pronounce since it is new language for them. Analysis of speech is important in the authentic topic materials that contribute to their tasks for enhancement of their communication competency and delivery during the oral presentation. It is designed for enhancing students in their delivery of their speech (Castillo Losada, Insuasty, Osorio, & Fernanda, 2017). Speaking must be audible in their presentation so that audience will clearly understand the presentation. Proper enunciation, diction or pronunciation must be given emphasis for a clearer view of the topic to be presented. Confidence must be developed by the students since speaking is a skill in their module.

Moreover, execution of the oral presentation in the area of personal energy shows good rating where the students are confident during the presentation. Developing confident skills will give an impact during the oral presentation. Personal energy helps guide the presenter to be more confident and control nervousness. Preparation is needed as reflected in the oral presentation. It is vital to speak with confidence; explain personal experiences and have thorough knowledge on the topic presented. It makes the speaker comfortable in style and in manner of speaking in front of the audience. Also they should execute well and easily exercising the different kinds of voice and speech capability (Chang, 2018). The accessibility of the speech development allows students to learn opportunities to practice in the public speaking because techniques are taught to improve the communication process of the students. It is a promising learning experience of the students because they can explore their knowledge in public speaking and it is a challenge among the students in the actual setting of learning (Schneider, Börner, Van Rosmalen, & Specht, 2016).

However, execution of the oral presentation in the area of audience impact is moderate. Audience impact helps students to develop their skills and confidence in the oral presentation since they feel the support of each other. Their morale is boosted because of the support of the members of the class. It helps the presenters to gain confidence as they present their oral task in the public. Preparation is needed, for instance PowerPoint presentation and materials needed in the oral presentation. Preparation in the execution of their presentation can lead the learners to be effective in their own way of executing their presentation. This is the tool for the students to know.

This can provide cue on the sequence of the execution of the oral presentation. It can help the audience in identifying what is executed in the oral presentation. Audience applauds the presenter/s as support in the oral presentation which helps presenter/s gain confidence in the task they are doing (Moulton, Türkay, & Kosslyn, 2017). However, audience can give feedback on the oral presentation whether negative or positive for better improvement of the learning process of the students. Feedback must be positively taken into consideration as part of the student learning. The competency in the oral presentation depends on the feedback on the presentation. The audience observes for the better impact of the presentation. This can be done by the module tutor, peer and other audience in the crowd during the presentation. It requires self-assessment in underlying knowledge possessed by the presenter/s (van Ginkel, Gulikers, Biemans, & Mulder, 2017).

Finally, execution of the oral presentation in the area of time management is moderate which means the flow of the presentation is smooth, however; there is a need to maximise time properly to cope with the objectives set during the presentation. Rest assured that objectives of the presentation must be tackled accordingly. Remember that oral presentation is an effective when time is used appropriately. It must be equally divided on the time given to the task. Management of time effectively in the oral presentation should be allocated on the task given among the members of the group. Determine the topic to be delivered, start on time and end on time which includes the sequence of the slides to be presented (Livingston, Perry, & Prager, 2017).

6. Conclusion

Performance level of students in the area of content of their oral presentation on the introduction reveals poor, key points and body is good, conclusion is moderate and references is moderate. However; in the area of execution of their oral presentation, speech reveals poor, personal energy is good, audience impact and time management is moderate.

On the other hand, when two variables (content and execution) are tested against each other, it reveals that all computed r-value is lower than the critical r-value of 0.361. Therefore, there is no significant relationship between the content of the oral presentation and the execution of the oral presentation among the respondents, the hypothesis is accepted and the null hypothesis is rejected.

7. Recommendation

- 1) Students must be guided properly on how to introduce their topic to give clear view points among the audience because content of the oral presentation is affected. This is to give an idea of what is the topic all about. The key points must be given emphasis among the respondents to improve more on the content of their oral presentation, this can lead to a better result of the conclusion in their

oral presentation so with the references which are important in the oral presentation, giving emphasis on the standard format of Harvard referencing to include text citation.

- 2) Students should practice their oral presentation because this has an impact on their speech if words are mispronounced that can lead confusion to the audience. They need to develop self-confidence to gain personal energy. They should be prepared enough to have a better audience impact. They also need to maximise time management in the execution of their oral presentation so that objectives in the oral presentation are not affected.

References

- Castillo Losada, C. A., Insuasty, E. A., Osorio, J., & Fernanda, M. (2017). The impact of authentic materials and tasks on students' communicative competence at a Colombian language school. *Profile Issues in Teachers Professional Development*, 19(1), 89-104.
- Çetin, P. S., & Eymur, G. (2017). Developing students' scientific writing and presentation skills through argument driven inquiry: an exploratory study. *Journal of Chemical Education*, 94(7), 837-843.
- Chang, M. (2018). *Public Speaking—From Preparation to Presentation: How to Become Confident, Relaxed and Meaningful*.
- Drew, S. (2018). *The student skills: guide*. Routledge.
- Endo, T., Watanabe, T., & Yamamoto, A. (2015). Confidence interval estimation by bootstrap method for uncertainty quantification using random sampling method. *Journal of Nuclear Science and Technology*, 52(7-8), 993-999.
- Li, X., Li, C., Chi, J., & Ouyang, J. (2018). Short text topic modeling by exploring original documents. *Knowledge and Information Systems*, 56(2), 443-462.
- Liang, H. Y., & Kelsen, B. (2018). Influence of personality and motivation on oral presentation performance. *Journal of psycholinguistic research*, 47(4), 755-776.
- Lin, C. J., & Hwang, G. J. (2018). A learning analytics approach to investigating factors affecting EFL students' oral performance in a flipped classroom. *Journal of Educational Technology & Society*, 21(2), 205-219.
- Livingston, S. O., Perry, E. L., & Prager, S. H. (2017). U.S. Patent No. 9,582,167. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- Hanusch, F., & Tandoc Jr, E. C. (2019). Comments, analytics, and social media: The impact of audience feedback on journalists' market orientation. *Journalism*, 20(6), 695-713.
- Krippendorff, K. (2018). *Content analysis: An introduction to its methodology*. Sage publications.
- Moulton, S. T., Türkay, S., & Kosslyn, S. M. (2017). Does a presentation's medium affect its message? PowerPoint, Prezi, and oral presentations. *PloS one*, 12(7), e0178774.

- Murillo-Zamorano, L. R., & Montanero, M. (2018). Oral presentations in higher education: a comparison of the impact of peer and teacher feedback. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 43(1), 138-150.
- Omar, A. (2015). Selecting the appropriate study design for your research: Descriptive study designs. *Journal of Health Specialties*, 3(3), 153.
- Poonpon, K. (2017). Enhancing English skills through project-based learning. *The English Teacher*, 10.
- Ringeisen, T., Rohrman, S., Bürgermeister, A., & Tibubos, A. N. (2017). Assessing self-efficacy in presentation and moderation skills: Validation of a new scale (SEPM).
- Signoret, C., Johnsrude, I., Classon, E., & Rudner, M. (2018). Combined effects of form- and meaning-based predictability on perceived clarity of speech. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 44(2), 277.
- Stuart, E. A., & Grove, B. A. (2017). U.S. Patent No. 9,684,901. Washington, DC: U.S. Patent and Trademark Office.
- vanGinkel, S., Gulikers, J., Biemans, H., & Mulder, M. (2017). Fostering oral presentation performance: does the quality of feedback differ when provided by the teacher, peers or peers guided by tutor?. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*, 42(6), 953-966.
- vanGinkel, S., Gulikers, J., Biemans, H., & Mulder, M. (2017). The impact of the feedback source on developing oral presentation competence. *Studies in Higher Education*, 42(9), 1671-1685.
- Wlodkowski, R. J., & Ginsberg, M. B. (2017). *Enhancing adult motivation to learn: A comprehensive guide for teaching all adults*. John Wiley & Sons.
- Yap, J. M., Groen, C., Kamilova, Y., Terzi, P., & Zvonareva, D. (2018). What went wrong? A five-school review of Master's theses reference list. *The Reference Librarian*, 59(4), 225-234.

Creative Commons licensing terms

Authors will retain the copyright of their published articles agreeing that a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License (CC BY 4.0) terms will be applied to their work. Under the terms of this license, no permission is required from the author(s) or publisher for members of the community to copy, distribute, transmit or adapt the article content, providing a proper, prominent and unambiguous attribution to the authors in a manner that makes clear that the materials are being reused under permission of a Creative Commons License. Views, opinions and conclusions expressed in this research article are views, opinions and conclusions of the author(s). Open Access Publishing Group and European Journal of Applied Linguistics Studies shall not be responsible or answerable for any loss, damage or liability caused in relation to/arising out of conflict of interests, copyright violations and inappropriate or inaccurate use of any kind content related or integrated on the research work. All the published works are meeting the Open Access Publishing requirements and can be freely accessed, shared, modified, distributed and used in educational, commercial and non-commercial purposes under a [Creative Commons attribution 4.0 International License \(CC BY 4.0\)](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/).